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More than Turbulence

Presentation · February 2020

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MORE THAN TURBULENCE

DISOBEY.FI 2020

CHRIS KUBECKA, CEO HYPASEC

PRESENTER

- Cyber warfare incident management EMEA, governments
- Critical infrastructure security: Oil & Gas, Water, Maritime, Aviation, Energy & Nuclear
- Former Head of Aramco Information Protection
- Former U.S Air Force Aviator
- Former USAF Space Command

C-5 GALAXY LOADMASTER

DO YOU WANT HACKERS

**BECAUSE THATS
HOW YOU GET HACKERS**

Chris Kubecka @SecEvangelism

SECURITY & PRIVACY CHALLENGES

Large number
of access
points

Legacy
Equipment

IP theft

Profits over
vulnerabilities

3rd parties

Security an
afterthought

MOTIVATIONS

- Create safer airspace
- Lion Air Flight 610
- Ethiopian Airlines Flight 302
- >300 Deaths
- Previous experience with in-flight emergencies

Chris Kubecka @SecEvangelism

BOEING & EXOSTAR

- No vulnerability disclosure program
- General bad coding practices
- General bad digital security
- Legal danger zone

```
<!-- ### BEGIN FOOTER ### -->
<!--<div class="prefooter">
<p><a href="http://www.boeing.com/companyoffices/aboutus/site_terms.html" tabindex="">Site
Terms</a> | <a href="http://www.boeing.com/companyoffices/aboutus/privacy.html" tabindex="">
Privacy Policy</a> | <a href="http://www.boeing.com/contactus.html" tabindex="">Contact Us</a> |
<a href="http://www.boeing.com/faqs.html" tabindex="">FAQ</a></p>
</div> -->
<div id="footer"><center>
<p>Copyright &copy; 1995 - 2019 Boeing. All rights
reserved.</p>
<!--
<br/>
#no idea what this was trying to print but only says
</center></div>
<!-- ### END FOOTER ### -->
<center>
<font color="gray" size="2">
<p>
</p></center>
<br>
</center>
</font>
<p><font color="gray" size="2"></font></p></center></div>
<!-- Adobe Analytics Code -->
<script type="text/javascript">
if (typeof _satellite !== "undefined") {
_satellite.pageBottom();
} else {
```

Then the other side to see what for instance general coding practices look from the outside. This is from the Boeing aviationID login website

04/08/19, 17:25 ✓

LOL - you probably shouldn't extrapolate from the web site to flight control code.

BOEING & EXOSTAR

```
<!-- #no idea what this was trying to print but only says NULL -->  
</center></div>
```

BOEING REPORT

- High Threat Profile
- Safety concerns
- National security
- Insecure access
- Low password complexity
- Spoof the CEO's email

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BOEING & EXOSTAR

- Bypass authentication using a button
- Access to flight control R&D
- Development servers wide open
- Little to Zero encryption
- Outdated ciphers
- Decode SAML = hardcoded creds

ULTIMATE FACEPALM

Because sometimes even a Double Facepalm doesn't cut it.

BOEING REPORT

- Public relations revenge
- Legal danger zone
- Threats to reputation
- Previous researchers ruined
- Previous whistleblowers blacklisted

BOEING REPORT

done on purpose. Boeing has threatened: [paraphrase] Any security researcher who discloses any vulnerabilities or exploitable conditions. We [Boeing] will turn our entire legal and PR apparatus to take legal action, obtain cease and desist orders and ruin the reputation of the researcher.

BOEING ISSUES

- Lack of encryption
- Email delivered malware
- Email domain spoofing
- Weak/Outdated remote management
- 3rd party coding Exostar

BOEING ISSUES

21 / 71

21 engines detected this file

a1fcd004d07ec2eaf0fa3b4d56d9b1b2ee30d36f19111454f20fddfdcd1ee50fc

Community Score

nxdomain peexe

Detailed description: This is a screenshot of a VirusTotal scan result. On the left, a circular gauge shows '21 / 71' engines. To the right, a red warning icon is followed by the text '21 engines detected this file'. Below this is a long alphanumeric hash: 'a1fcd004d07ec2eaf0fa3b4d56d9b1b2ee30d36f19111454f20fddfdcd1ee50fc'. Underneath the hash is a 'Community Score' section with a question mark icon and a progress bar. At the bottom, there are two tags: 'nxdomain' and 'peexe'.

EXOSTAR RESPONSE

The email you sent on 5 August 2019 08:36 local time appears to have been written by an attorney. As such, it feels like a little bit of censorship by what the EFF call a chilling effect.

At the present moment, a division of the Department of Homeland Security has requested I coordinate the technical specifics with only them. This is in accordance with local Netherlands laws which stipulate certain conditions for exchanging vulnerability information in what we call "responsible disclosure" in most of Europe. Once a governmental authority is involved, I am mandated to work directly with them in this case, the government authority where the company is domiciled. I am a Dutch resident, all reseach took place in accordance with Dutch laws in The Netherlands. Censorship is illegal in The Netherlands.

Employees of Boeing and the US aviation ISACA were made aware of the coordinated responsible disclosure with DHS. The full report is only available to DHS per their request. Lastly, DHS has requested I make them aware of any person or company trying to threaten in a litigious manner, bully or censor me regarding the report. I sincerely hope this was not your company lawyer's intention.

Thanks,

Chris

US AVIATION ISAC RESPONSE

I happen to be a Boeing employee also operating the Aviation ISAC.

Doug Boeing
18:00, The Platinum Hotel & Spa

A-ISAC CEO Jeff Troy disputes this claim. Troy says that a meeting between Kubecka and Blough occurred in a coffee shop in Las Vegas during Black Hat in August 2019 to discuss the matter but denies that an NDA was requested and any threats were made. "Obviously, we take this

BOEING REPORT FEEDBACK

Email infection: Vendor engaged their IR team to review. No evidence of infection found

Email server lacking DMARC: Currently in the process of deploying

SAML Credential Standards: Possible to decode but the NIST 8663 standard is in place

Exposed development systems: Currently in the process of updating to DMARC

Exposed development systems: The system while exposed is performing as intended

FTP server: Planning an upgrade to SSH

Password complexity: working to develop a stronger password policy

BOEING REPORT FEEDBACK

EPIC FAIL

Ordinary failure wasn't enough.

J.M. PORUP @TOHOLDAQUILL CSO IDG MEDIA

The most damning revelation Kubecka uncovered, however, is that at least one of Boeing's email servers is infected with multiple strains of malware. According to the Virus Total malware database, which is owned and managed by Google, [multiple varieties of malware on one of Boeing's email servers are phoning home](#). Clicking through on the malware hashes listed reveals a wide variety of malware communicating with Boeing's email server when opened or executed.

BOEING WITH LOOKING GLASS SCOUT PRIME

▶ [Ponyloader Infection](#) 1 Elements ▾
Source: [LookingGlass Reputation](#)
Tic Score: 69

ACTIVE THREATS	COLLECTIONS	LAST ACTIVITY	TIC SCORE
1	1	1 day ago	67 +57 points since 12/27/2019

Boeing

RULES (1) NOTES (0)

ASN 0 | CIDRV4 2 | FQDN 0 | IP

ELEMENT SEVERITY

0 CRITICAL	3 ELEVATED
---------------	---------------

THREATS (1)

0 CRITICAL	1 ELEVATED
---------------	---------------

BOEING WITH LOOKING GLASS SCOUT PRIME

Ponyloader Infection

ELEMENTS (338274)

[ELEMENT HISTORY](#)

Filter Elements

SORT BY: TIC ▾

ELEMENTS

338274

COLLECTIONS

1

▶ [34.219.36.191](#)

Tis Secret 100

FBI & SECURITIES & EXCHANGE COMMISSION

- Requested to ask FBI to open an investigation
 - Coercion
- 2017 Guidance for aircraft cybersecurity
- Undisclosed Boeing R&D Breach 2018
- SEC Legal Team
- Whistleblower Protection

FBI & SECURITIES & EXCHANGE COMMISSION

2018

APX of Month of September 2018 Individuals finds Boeing open server (rumored Building 2-15 lab). Boeing software relating to 737 Max and 787 was copied from server. It is unknown what other software was collected or exposed, not what other systems or servers were accessed.

2019

Week of July 22th Boeing contacts the airlines to discuss upcoming Black Hat disclosure

Week of July 29th Boeing briefs the airlines

Week of August 5th Black Hat presentation

September 6th Boeing Issues Service Letter Subject, "Enhanced Airplane Software Security Consistent with DO-355/ED204

(RTCA DO-355, "Information Security Guidance for Continued Airworthiness")

FBI & SECURITIES & EXCHANGE COMMISSION

It is going to be a bumpy ride for you.. reminds me to about 7-8 years ago when our team got blacklisted for whistle blowing on corruption.

But stick with it, it will be worth it!

But they are a big corp and they will try to exhaust you

Nov 6, 2019, 9:09 AM

I was told verbally yesterday that Boeing had the dreamliner pentest buried by the us government because they didn't like the report and the engineers refused to change it

BOEING IOT CABIN VIEWING SYSTEM

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar displaying 'Not secure [redacted]'. The page title is 'CABIN VIDEO MONITORING SYSTEM'. A sidebar on the left contains navigation items: Dashboard, Live Stream, Watch, Media, and Fleet Management. The main content area is titled 'CVMS - DASHBOARD' and 'Airplanes'. It contains a table with the following data:

Registration Number ↑	Connectivity	Serial Number	Airplane Model	Owner	Operator	Lessee
BON [redacted]	✓	[redacted]	777-9	CEN	N/A	N/A
KID [redacted]	✗	[redacted]	777-300ER	KID	KID	N/A
NX [redacted]	✓	[redacted]	777-8	CVMS	N/A	N/A

BOEING IMPROVEMENT (?)

- Vulnerability Disclosure Program
- No PGP Key
- October 2019 installed TLS Certificate
- Boeing Escalation with Media
- Boeing escalation with DHS ICS
- Twitter attacks against journalist
- Exostar has no VDP

SOLUTIONS

- Hackers aren't criminals
- Low cost non-destructive testing
- Involving more stakeholders
- Improving image with the public
- Fixing before criminals leverage
- Make this routine

**RECOGNISING
SECURITY**

**TAKING
VULNERABILITY
REPORTS**

**WORKING
WITH DHS/GOV**

**SOLVING ISSUES
B4 PROBLEMS**

THANK YOU

- Thank you: J.M. Porup, DHS ICS-CERT, Looking Glass Cyber, BBC
- Hacking the World with OSINT & Censys
- Down the Rabbit Hole an OSINT Journey
- en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chris_Kubecka

